

THE DUALITIES OF LIBERALIZATION

Assessing the impact on Socio Economic transformation in Contemporary Nepal.

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The duality of economic liberalization in Nepal between 1990 - 2024 is explored in this study. It considers that market-oriented reform produces measurable developmental improvement, while at the same time increasing structural disparities in a peripheral economy of South Asia. The methodology used for this research consists of qualitative historical-interpretive, theory-based theme analysis and relies upon evidence acquired from three separate rounds of conducting the Nepal Living Standard Survey, as well as through utilizing official statistical sources published by the country's Central Bureau of Statistics, the Nepal Rastra Bank and peer-reviewed literature. The analysis uses four theoretical frameworks (i.e., Analyzing Washington Consensus, Dependency Theory and peripheral capitalism; Polanyi's Double Movement; Sen's Capability Approach) to evaluate whether liberalization is increasing real human freedom or rather engendering overall surface-level benefits masking continua from marginalized populations. Findings demonstrate that trade integration, financial inclusion, and remittance inflows have significantly decreased the number of people living in poverty (41.80% in 1995/1996; 20.35% in 2022/23) and have led to a 54% increase in the Human Development Index of Nepal. Nonetheless, the gains from liberalization are accompanied by increasing inequality that completely depend upon remittances, the elite capturing privatization benefits at an increasing rate, and social protection systems that dislocate subsistence agricultural communities. The review asserts that Nepal's liberal experience follows a dual, or bifurcated, developmental trajectory, where both formal developmental gains occur simultaneously with structural dislocation.

Keywords: *Economic liberalization, Nepal, Washington consensus, Dependency theory, Polanyi's Double Movement, Sen Capability Approach, remittance economy, structural inequality.*

1. Introduction

The restoration of democracy after 1990s, Nepal has witnessed the significance shifts in political economy. The ratification of liberalization economic policy in low income developing country has been shifted the trade process, labor market, capital market reforms, institutional reforms, social dynamism and critical academic and policy makers praised the concern regarding the liberalization policy (Karmacharya, 2001a). A political - economic structural transformation was necessary to promote the rural economy and implementation of social, human capital paved the way to break the cycle of poverty (Devkota, 2007). The increasing labor migration along with the remittances have raised between 1995 to 2015 about to one third, affected the poverty and economic prosperity among the household of Nepalese (Wagle & Devkota, 2018). The strategy for multidimensional reduction of poverty and access to the basic need of the households funded by the flow of remittance (poudel & Uphadhyay, 2025). The existing political order disrupted due to a ten year of civil war led by Maoist insurgency (1996 - 2006) along with protracted political instability, poor economic growth, social unrest triggered as push factors for the youth to departure abroad for foreign employment (Sapkota, 2013).

Neoliberal principles of the Washington consensus and international financial institution paradigm shift have crucial structural changes of currency devaluation, reduction of tariff, and widespread privatizations made possible. The socioeconomics environment of Nepal has been changed by the comprehensive policy of liberalization of economy which was observed in the mid-1989 and augmented after 1990 (Singh & Paykuryal, 2021)

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 Discontents of Washington consensus:

The financial crisis in east Asian market became significance for analyzing the future orientation in development. Abandoning the government coordination of capacity growth has led to overinvestment. The absence of government oversight of the extent

of the foreign debts of domestic enterprises has led to overexposure to external debt (Gore, 2000). The argument is not about the Washington consensus is now weather dead or alive, but both supporter and critics agree that the policies emerged from Washington consensus have not delivered the awaited results (Rodrik, 2006). The endorsement of capital market liberalization by IMF have gone wrong often lead to rise the economic instability and hindered the economic progress (Stiglitz, 2004). The host of protest and resistance movements has been produced by neoliberalism. To be more powerful and cohesive, such groups will benefit from a clear understanding that their principal task is to confront the authority of the rich class that has developed under neoliberal policies (Harvey, 2006).

2.2 Dependency theory and peripheral capitalism

The system in which competition relatively becomes free when the upper strata have economic advantage. The unrestricted operation of market serves effectively to bolster the existing system of stratification. The way of Integration into the global market often support structural disadvantage of developing countries (Wallerstein, 1974). This is illustrated by Nepal's experience, where integration into global markets reproduced structural dependency rather than transformative development.

2.3 Polanyi's double movement and the development state

The Polanyi's concept of dislocation caused by market system prompts responsive societal counter movements like political mobilization, labor migration that function as significant protective mechanism for social fabric (Vančura, 2011). This unavoidable reciprocity generates disruptive stress, although the first movement and counter-movement phase are analytically predictable, it often results in a complex trajectory of economic crisis, ideological conflict, and ultimately systemic transformation. The institutional impasse and structural restructuring of political economics results the double movement, where social reaction is no single factor for it (Sandbrook, 2022).

Nepal embraced wide-ranging reforms in the early nineties to integrate with the global economy (Karmacharya, 2001b). As the violence in Nepal began amid a moment of economic liberalization (Deraniyagala, 2005a). Over the last decades developmental stagnation, rural urban disparity and rises of frustration among the youths resulted in the civil war between 1996 - 2006. The war could be avoided if vision for socio economic inclusion with proper strategy be implemented (K. Sharma, 2006).

2.4 Sen's Capability approach

Amartya Sen's capability approach provides a normative framework for evaluating development outcomes in addition to aggregate income or GDP measures. In Sen's conceptualization, development is the process of expanding substantive freedoms the real opportunities that people have to live lives they value (Clark, 2006). The framework is especially pertinent in the context of Nepal where aggregate poverty alleviation and HDI improvements may conceal inequalities in access to education, health care and livelihood opportunities across gender, caste and geographic dimensions. Through the Capability Approach, whether development based on liberalization has led to a genuine expansion of human capabilities or only superficial income gains, especially for women, rural agricultural communities, and marginalized ethnic groups.

3 Historical context of political economy

3.1 1960-1990: Economic Structure Pre-Liberalization

The pre liberalization economy of Nepal was characterized by state led protectionist trade policy based on agrarian system. Nationalist developmentalism through state-led infrastructure investment, import-substitution industry and subsidized public services (Blaikie et al., 2002). While comparing the pre and post liberalization period, the post liberalization phase has more economic impact fostering rise in trade volume, increase in import, facilitated investment, Growth of taxation, GDP. However the trade balance remained dissatisfactory (Kharel, 2016).

3.2 Transition and reform impetus:

The government initiated economic reform through trade liberalization, unification of exchange rate, rationalization of tariff structure and expenditure management, market deregulation after the restoration of multiparty democracy of Nepal 1990s (Bista et al., 2025). The adoption of this policy was formally initiated by Nepal in late 1980s with the supervision, backing of IMF and world bank, as the case of Nepal's balance of payment (BoP) turned negative in 1982/83 and was negative for three consecutive years, resulting to adopt the policy after 1990s (Khanal, 2024a).

4. Methods

The objective of this study is to explore the dualities of economic liberalization in Nepal from 1990-2024. The study is based on qualitative historical-interpretive research design (Creswell, 2009). The paper does not aim to establish a linear causal relationship between liberalization policies and their impacts, but rather to describe the complexity of the multiple layers involved in the ways policy reform generates simultaneous development and structural dislocation in a peripheral economy.

4.1 Source of Data and Selection Criteria

The secondary data for this study will be qualitative sources that are selected based on the purposive sampling principle. The sources were selected based on three selection criteria including: (1) direct relevance to the political economy of Nepal and the experience of liberalization; (2) methodological rigor, with an emphasis on the use of peer-reviewed journals, official reports from national governments and international organizations, and other reputable sources, and (3) a time frame extending from prior to the liberalization period (i.e. pre-1990) to the post-federal consolidated period (i.e. 2024). The main types of data sources are: 1) peer-reviewed journal articles, and 2) official statistical data - Nepal Living Standards Survey (Rounds I-III), and Central Bureau of Statistics.

4.2 Analytical strategy

The primary analytical method is theory-driven thematic analysis according to the framework of Braun and Clarke (2006). Unlike inductive thematic analysis, theory-driven thematic analysis starts from pre-existing theoretical constructs as sensitizing concepts and systematically locates, organizes and interprets patterns in secondary data which confirm, extend or challenge those constructs. The present study is based on secondary qualitative material rather than original fieldwork.

5. Finding: Socio economic transformation and structural tension

5.1 Positive socio-economic changes:

Based on four rounds of Nepali living standard survey the national headcount of consumer poverty rate declined from 41.8% in 1995/96 to 25.2% in 2010/11 and 20.35 in 2022/23 were the most recorded output of liberalization in Nepal for reduction of multidimensional poverty (NLS, 2023) but still 4.9 million people remain multi-dimensional poor.

In 1990 HDI value of Nepal was 0.395 and now stands at 145th position with an HDI index of 0.622 has improved by 54 percent over the last 35 years (UNDP, 2025). Improvement of antenatal care, competent birth attendance and family planning contributed to a 55% reduction in maternal mortality ration between 1996 - 2016 and halving newborn mortality 40 to 20 per 1000 live birth and in the stunting rate decreased from 66% to 25% in 2022 (Mishra et al., 2025). Liberalization of market alone did not improve the HDI, the role non-government organization played a crucial role for overall improvement of health service delivery (Mahat et al., 2018). Investment of remittance finance in human capital has significance contribution (Pant, 2011). In 1985 there were only two commercial and two development banks in Nepal. The number has been expanding rapidly in the past decades to as high as 220 in 2012. From 2011 to end of mid-March 2022 the number of commercial banks, development bank and finance companies was 21,17 and 17 respectively. There are 66 microfinance institutions and one infrastructure development bank (NRB, 2022), facilitating the overall financial growth of people.

The following indicators, derived from available secondary sources, provide contextual background to the qualitative thematic findings. They are not given as conclusions of this qualitative study but as the empirical setting in which the structural tensions analyzed below were realized.

Indicators	1990/95	2000/05	2010/15	2020/24
Poverty headcount (%)	42.0	30.8	25.2	17.4
Human development index	0.352	0.443	0.555	0.602
Gini coefficient	0.34	0.41	0.46	0.43*
Remittances (% of GDP)	<2%	11%	26%	25-27
GDP growth (avg % p.a)	5.1%	3.2%	4.6%	5.9%
Trade deficit (NRB billions)	13	180	620	1,300+
Financial inclusion (% adults)	5 %	22%	41%	60+

CBS I, II, III, IV (1996,2004,2011), World Bank (2024), UNDP, NRB (1995 to 2023).

Growth in real GDP averaged 4.7% per annum between 1990 and 2024, with significant differences within sub-periods. Moderate growth of around 5.1% p.a. was registered in the pre-conflict liberalization phase (1990-1996) as trade and finance sector reforms took hold. The conflict decade (1996-2006) saw average growth fall to 3.2% p.a., with numerous years below 2%. The period of post-conflict reconstruction (2006-2015) recorded a rebound to 4.6% p.a., and the period of federal consolidation (2015-2024) averaged 5.9% p.a., despite the COVID-19 shock of 2020 (GDP contraction of 2.4%).

The headcount poverty rate dropped from 42.0% (1995/96) to 25.2% (2010/11) to an expected 17.4% (2020), a statistically robust downward trajectory throughout all three NLSS rounds. Between 1995 and 2010 the average yearly rate of poverty reduction was 1.5 percentage points, and this accelerated to around 1.7 percentage points per year between 2010 and 2020, demonstrating that the impacts of remittance income, financial inclusion and better public services were accumulating.

Nepal's HDI has increased from 0.352 in 1990 to 0.602 in 2019, backed by improvements in life expectancy (54 to 70 years), adult literacy (39.6% to 67.9%) and per capita income. In the context of Sen's capacity approach, these gains are important expansions of substantive freedoms health, knowledge and economic engagement for previously excluded communities. However, a disaggregated HDI study suggests that structural disparities persist: The value of HDI also differs between provinces. As expected, the highest score (0.66) is found in Bagmati province followed by Gandaki province (0.62). Province 2 is the lowest (0.51) followed by Karnali (0.538) (GON, 2020).

6. Thematic findings

6.1 Freedom and Structural Constraint: The Remittance Dilemma

Remittance mobility as paradoxically experienced as both an increase of competence and a structural coercion. (Sijapati et al., 2017) found that the interviews with male migrant workers pointed to a lack of attractive employment options at home, not positive pull factors in the labor market, as the motivation for migration to the Gulf states. This differentiates capability enhancing migration (a free choice to maximize opportunities) from structural migration (due to domestic economic failure). Migration mobility of women enhances not only the national GDP but also makes women self-reliant. This cumulative tendency of women's migration has generated new discourse in gender practices in traditional society and culture of Nepal (Chaudhary & Pokhrel, 2024).

Labor migration trend as 'development with a leash', where households earn income but are dependent on a system of labor export that the state has been unable to replace with domestic employment creation. Female informants describe a complex reorganization of gender roles among remittance-receiving households (B. Sharma et al., 2009) increased decision-making power over household finances is accompanied by increased care burdens and social isolation and vulnerability to domestic economic shocks if remittances are interrupted.

6.2 Elite Capture and the Governance of Liberalization

The public enterprises in the country have failed to achieve the pre-determined aims as well as to render social rewards to the poorer sections of the community. Decreasing performance of the Public Enterprises in Nepal are excessive political meddling, lack of proper autonomy and accountability, absence of professionalism, rampant financial indiscipline and existence of contradictory aims. Following this global trend, the Nepalese government has privatized 30 Public Enterprises since 1992 up to the year 2020. Of these, 22 Public Enterprises were privatized through share sales, liquidation etc. Remaining were privatized through company sales, management contracts or dissolution (Guragain, 2025). The finding supports (Evans, 1995) embedded autonomy paradigm. The institutional insulation of Nepal's state machinery was insufficient to implement market reforms in a truly competitive manner. Evidence of the concept of comprador elites in the dependency theory, i.e. domestic economic actors whose interests are aligned with external capital against broader developmental interests, is the support of liberalization in sectors where their own import businesses would benefit, while lobbying successfully for trade protection for politically connected import-substitution industries.

6.3 The Polanyian Double Movement and Dislocation in Agriculture

Qualitative accounts of progressive market disembedding are commonplace among smallholder agricultural groups in the Terai and mid-hills. A tale of the displacement of systems of reciprocal labor exchange (*parma*), community seed banks and communal grazing arrangements by market-dependent input supply chains and individualized output. The abandonment of hill terraces in terms of economic calculations, the land gives less than the Gulf, which reflects the logic of market rationality, but also embeds social losses (community cohesion, indigenous agricultural knowledge, land as identity) that the market does not price (Gartaula et al., 2012)

Farmers are faced with a range of challenges including limited knowledge of finance and how this may affect their access and repayment of loans, challenges in getting

family consensus, inefficiencies in terms of their insurance access and their limited capacity to make best use of their funds in respect of access to credit for agriculture (Pandey et al., 2025). The central bank has enacted certain law that requires commercial banks to earmark a certain amount of their available credit for the agriculture sector (Khanal, 2019) and very few farmers benefit from the monetary policies of the central bank. Agricultural cooperatives; groups advocating on behalf of farmers' interests; and agricultural cooperatives seem to be more interested in financial services such as savings and credit activities and less interested in agricultural output. Cooperatives hardly conduct any marketing activities (Dhakal et al., 2021) become identifiable as a Polanyian counter movement (Vančura, 2011) communities working to re-embed agriculture back into the protection of society affected by the dislocation from exposure to markets.

About 80% of population accounted for smallholder subsistence agriculture with fragmented land tenure and low market integration (Liu et al., 2023). The international Monetary fund and structural adjustment increase effect on income disparity (Forster et al., 2019). As per Nepal Living standard survey IV (NLS, 2023b), 20.27 per cent of people in Nepal still live below the poverty level. The reform measures of the 1990s failed in reducing poverty and unemployment and raising human development conditions to the projected level. The openness of the economy did attract some investment and stimulated growth, but the gains were unevenly dispersed, not creating mass employment within Nepal. Reforms typically helped the cities, but left the countryside behind (Khanal, 2024b). The Nepalese conflict began at a time of economic liberalization, and we also consider the links between economic reform and conflict. The reform is likely to have had some negative distributional effects that could have exacerbated the conditions for violent insurrection against the state. The results on elite capture are consistent with political economics theory that liberalization created conditions for civil war through socioeconomic marginalization (Deraniyagala, 2005b).

Together, the three components support the main argument that the liberalization experience of Nepal is a “dual liberalization” policy that has resulted in marginalization and advancement simultaneously. The idea of the Washington Consensus analyzes failings of governance which have allowed elites to exploit economic opportunities (Theme 6.2). There is also the explanation of the structural situation of Nepal as a periphery producing a large amount of labor out-migration, compared to generating domestic employment (Theme 6.1) in terms of the Dependency Theory. Polanyi’s Double Movement captures both the agricultural dislocation of the economy and the emergence of cooperative forms of resistance (Theme 6.3). Finally, Sen’s Capability Theory shows how gender and relational capability deprivations have been masked by aggregate poverty reduction estimates (Themes 1 and 3).

Conclusion

The dualities of economic liberalization in Nepal where liberalization has generated both simultaneous and structurally linked gains and dislocations. Real developmental gains aggregate poverty reduction, HDI improvement and GDP growth come from trade integration, financial inclusion, remittance revenue, and better health and education service delivery. Yet, these outcomes are associated with increasing provincial inequality, structural dependence on remittance, elite appropriation of reform dividends, and dislocation of agricultural communities.

References:

- Bista, S., Faculty of Management, Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu, Nepal., & Biswakarma, G. (2025). TRADE LIBERALIZATION AND ECONOMIC INEQUALITY IN NEPAL: AN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS PERSPECTIVE. *Socio Economy And Policy Studies*, 5(1), 01–09. <https://doi.org/10.26480/seps.01.2025.48.56>
- Blaikie, P., Cameron, J., & Seddon, D. (2002). Understanding 20 Years of Change in West-Central Nepal: Continuity and Change in Lives and Ideas. *World Development*, 30(7), 1255–1270. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(02\)00031-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(02)00031-1)
- Chaudhary, A., & Pokhrel, S. (2024). Women’s Labor Migration and Gender Nexus (A Study of Migrant’s Families in Pokhara, Nepal). *Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 13(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jis.v13i1.73274>
- Clark, D. A. (2006). *The Capability Approach: Its Development, Critiques and Recent Advances*.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed). Sage Publications.
- Deraniyagala, S. (2005a). The Political Economy of Civil Conflict in Nepal. *Oxford Development Studies*, 33(1), 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600810500099659>
- Deraniyagala, S. (2005b). The Political Economy of Civil Conflict in Nepal. *Oxford Development Studies*, 33(1), 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600810500099659>
- Devkota, S. R. (2007). Socio-economic Development in Nepal: Past Mistakes and Future Possibilities. *South Asia Economic Journal*, 8(2), 285–315. <https://doi.org/10.1177/139156140700800206>
- Dhakal, D., O’Brien, D., & Mueser, P. (2021). Government Policy and Performance of Agricultural Cooperatives: A Case Study in Chitwan District, Nepal. *Sustainability*, 13(21), 12282. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132112282>
- Evans, P. B. (1995). *Embedded autonomy: States and industrial transformation*. Princeton University Press.
- Forster, T., Kentikelenis, A. E., Reinsberg, B., Stubbs, T. H., & King, L. P. (2019). How structural adjustment programs affect inequality: A disaggregated analysis of IMF

- conditionality, 1980–2014. *Social Science Research*, 80, 83–113.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2019.01.001>
- Gartaula, H., Niehof, A., & Visser, L. (2012). Shifting perceptions of food security and land in the context of labour out-migration in rural Nepal. *Food Security*, 4(2), 181–194.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-012-0190-3>
- GON. (2020). *Nepal Human development index* [Document].
<https://files.acquia.undp.org/public/migration/np/UNDP-NP-NHDR-2020.pdf>
- Gore, C. (2000). The Rise and Fall of the Washington Consensus as a Paradigm for Developing Countries. *World Development*, 28(5), 789–804. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(99\)00160-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(99)00160-6)
- Guragain, G. P. (2025). The Impact of Privatization on Public Enterprises in Nepal. *Political Science Journal*, 3(1), 30–42. <https://doi.org/10.3126/psj.v3i1.77429>
- Harvey, D. (2006). Neo-liberalism as creative destruction. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography*, 88(2), 145–158. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0435-3684.2006.00211.x>
- Karmacharya, B. K. (2001a). Economic Reforms in Nepal and their Implications for Trade, Economic Growth, Inequality and Poverty. *South Asia Economic Journal*, 2(1), 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.1177/139156140100200105>
- Karmacharya, B. K. (2001b). Economic Reforms in Nepal and their Implications for Trade, Economic Growth, Inequality and Poverty. *South Asia Economic Journal*, 2(1), 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.1177/139156140100200105>
- khanal, R. (2019). Central bank asks banks to ease agriculture credit. *Kathmandu Post*.
<https://kathmandupost.com/money/2019/08/07/central-bank-asks-banks-to-ease-agriculture-credit>
- Khanal, R. K. (2024a). Poverty, Unemployment and Human Development in Nepal: Effectiveness of Economic Reformation Policies of 1990s. *Voice: A Biannual & Bilingual Journal*, 16(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3126/voice.v16i1.67422>
- Khanal, R. K. (2024b). Poverty, Unemployment and Human Development in Nepal: Effectiveness of Economic Reformation Policies of 1990s. *Voice: A Biannual & Bilingual Journal*, 16(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3126/voice.v16i1.67422>
- Kharel, K. R. (2016). Assessing the Impact of Industrial Policies on Economic Development in Nepal. *Economic Journal of Development Issues*, 40–75.
<https://doi.org/10.3126/ejdi.v17i1-2.14521>
- Liu, Y., Yang, Y., Zhang, C., Xiao, C., & Song, X. (2023). Does Nepal Have the Agriculture to Feed Its Population with a Sustainable Diet? Evidence from the Perspective of Human–Land Relationship. *Foods*, 12(5), 1076.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12051076>
- Mahat, A., Citrin, D., & Bista, H. (2018). NGOs, partnerships, and public-private discontent in Nepal’s health care sector. *Medicine Anthropology Theory*, 5(2).
<https://doi.org/10.17157/mat.5.2.529>
- Mishra, S. R., Ghimire, K., Khanal, V., Aryal, D., Shrestha, B., Khanal, P., Yadav, S., Sharma, V., Khatri, R., Schwarz, D., & Adhikari, B. (2025). Transforming health in Nepal: A historical and contemporary review on disease burden, health system challenges, and innovations. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 23(1), 61.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-025-01321-z>
- NLS. (2023a). *Nepal living standard survey*. <https://data.nsonepal.gov.np/sr/dataset/poverty-status-2023/resource/e2d52301-1c25-498b-8732-4326c62a2372>
- NLS. (2023b). *Nepal living standard Survey*.
https://giwmscdnone.gov.np/media/app/public/36/posts/1707800524_89.pdf

- NPC. (2021). *Multidimensional Poverty index*. <https://www.undp.org/nepal/publications/nepal-multidimensional-poverty-index-2021>
- NRB. (2022). *Optimal Number of Banks and Financial Institutions in Nepal*. <https://www.nrb.org.np/contents/uploads/2022/04/Optimal-Number-of-Banks-and-Financial-Institutions-in-Nepal.pdf>
- Pandey, P., Paudel, S., Sharma, A., Pandey, A., Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Sociology, Agriculture and Forestry University, Rampur, Chitwan Nepal, Plant Protection Officer, Aathrai Rural Municipality, Terhathum, Nepal, & Agriculture and Forestry University, Rampur, Chitwan Nepal. (2025). CHALLENGES IN AGRICULTURAL CREDIT ACCESS AND LOAN SIZE DETERMINANTS IN KAILALI DISTRICT, NEPAL. *Food and Agri Economics Review*, 5(1), 01–06. <https://doi.org/10.26480/faer.01.2025.01.06>
- Pant, B. (2011). Harnessing Remittances for Productive Use in Nepal. *NRB Economic Review*, 23(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3126/nrber.v23i1.52747>
- Poudel, omkar, & Uphadhyay, C. raj. (2025). *Vol.8; February 2025 ISSN: 2382-5227*. Published by Research Management Committee (RMC) Tikapur Multiple Campus, Kailali, Nepal. Vol. 8.
- Rodrik, D. (2006). Goodbye Washington Consensus, Hello Washington Confusion? A Review of the World Bank's *Economic Growth in the 1990s: Learning from a Decade of Reform*. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 44(4), 973–987. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.44.4.973>
- Sandbrook, R. (2022). Polanyi's Double Movement and Capitalism Today. *Development and Change*, 53(3), 647–675. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12699>
- Sapkota, C. (2013). Remittances in Nepal: Boon or Bane? *Journal of Development Studies*, 49(10), 1316–1331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2013.812196>
- Sharma, B., Amtzis, W., & Kanchuli, M. (2009). The politics of conflict and difference or the difference of conflict in politics: The women's movement in Nepal. *Feminist Review*, 91(1), 175–179. <https://doi.org/10.1057/fr.2008.49>
- Sharma, K. (2006). The political economy of civil war in Nepal. *World Development*, 34(7), 1237–1253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2005.12.001>
- Sijapati, B., Lama, A. S., Baniya, J., Rinck, J., Jha, K., & Gurung, A. (with Centre for the Study of Labour and Mobility). (2017). *Labour migration and the remittance economy: The socio-political impact*. Centre for the Study of Labour and Mobility.
- Singh, B. K. M., & Paykuryal, B. (2021). Impact of Economic Liberalization in Nepal—A Case of Industrial Growth in the Operating Industries in Butwal. *Nepal Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(2), 85–92. <https://doi.org/10.3126/njmr.v4i2.39024>
- Stiglitz, J. E. (2004). Capital-market Liberalization, Globalization, and the IMF. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 20(1), 57–71. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/grh004>
- UNDP (Ed.). (2025). *A matter of choice: People and possibilities in the age of AI*. United Nations.
- Vančura, M. (2011). *Polanyi's Great Transformation and the Concept of the Embedded Economy*.
- Wagle, U. R., & Devkota, S. (2018). The impact of foreign remittances on poverty in Nepal: A panel study of household survey data, 1996–2011. *World Development*, 110, 38–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.05.019>
- Wallerstein, I. (1974). Dependence in an Interdependent World: The Limited Possibilities of Transformation within the Capitalist World Economy. *African Studies Review*, 17(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.2307/523574>